

PEDAGOGICAL POTENTIAL OF CLASSROOM DEBATES IN FOSTERING CRITICAL THINKING

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20439135>

Abstract: In today's educational environment, developing critical thinking has become a key objective of higher education. One effective pedagogical tool for fostering this skill is academic debate. This study aims to examine the pedagogical potential of debates in the learning process and their impact on the development of students' critical thinking. The article examines the theoretical foundations of using debates as an interactive teaching method and analyzes their role in developing the skills of argumentation, analysis, information evaluation, and position expression. Particular attention is paid to the pedagogical conditions for the effective organization of debates in the educational process. The results of the study demonstrate that the systematic use of debates promotes students' cognitive activity, the development of analytical thinking, communication skills, and the ability to reasonably discuss different points of view. It is concluded that debates have significant pedagogical potential and can be effectively used as a means of developing critical thinking in educational practice.

Key words: debates, critical thinking, interactive teaching methods, pedagogical potential, higher education, argumentation, communication skills, active learning.

Аңдатпа: Қазіргі білім беру ортасында сыни ойлауды дамыту жоғары білім берудің негізгі мақсатына айналды. Бұл дағдыны дамытудың тиімді педагогикалық құралдарының бірі - академиялық пікірталас. Бұл зерттеу оқу процесіндегі пікірталастардың педагогикалық әлеуетін және олардың студенттердің сыни ойлауын дамытуға әсерін зерттеуге бағытталған. Мақалада пікірталастарды интерактивті оқыту әдісі ретінде пайдаланудың теориялық негіздері қарастырылады және олардың дәлелдеу, талдау, ақпаратты бағалау және ұстанымды білдіру дағдыларын дамытудағы рөлі талданады. Білім беру процесінде пікірталастарды тиімді ұйымдастырудың педагогикалық шарттарына ерекше назар аударылады. Зерттеу нәтижелері пікірталастарды жүйелі түрде қолдану студенттердің танымдық белсенділігіне, аналитикалық ойлаудың, коммуникативтік дағдылардың дамуына және әртүрлі көзқарастарды ақылға қонымды түрде талқылау қабілетіне ықпал ететінін көрсетеді. Пікірталастардың айтарлықтай педагогикалық әлеуеті бар және оларды білім беру тәжірибесінде сыни ойлауды дамыту құралы ретінде тиімді пайдалануға болады деген қорытынды жасалды.

Түйін сөздер: пікірталастар, сыни ойлау, интерактивті оқыту әдістері, педагогикалық әлеует, жоғары білім, дәлелдеу, коммуникативтік дағдылар, белсенді оқыту.

Аннотация: В современной образовательной среде развитие критического мышления стало ключевой задачей высшего образования. Одним из эффективных педагогических инструментов для развития этого навыка являются академические дебаты. Цель данного исследования - изучить педагогический потенциал дебатов в учебном процессе и их влияние на развитие критического мышления студентов. В статье рассматриваются теоретические основы использования дебатов как

интерактивного метода обучения и анализируется их роль в развитии навыков аргументации, анализа, оценки информации и выражения позиции. Особое внимание уделяется педагогическим условиям эффективной организации дебатов в учебном процессе. Результаты исследования показывают, что систематическое использование дебатов способствует познавательной активности студентов, развитию аналитического мышления, коммуникативных навыков и способности к обоснованному обсуждению различных точек зрения. Сделан вывод о том, что дебаты обладают значительным педагогическим потенциалом и могут эффективно использоваться как средство развития критического мышления в образовательной практике.

Ключевые слова: дебаты, критическое мышление, интерактивные методы обучения, педагогический потенциал, высшее образование, аргументация, коммуникативные навыки, активное обучение.

Introduction. In the modern educational process, which is focused on personal development and fostering a proactive approach to life, methods that foster the development of a key skill essential for successful self-realization – communicative competence are particularly relevant. According to the State Program for the Implementation of Language Policy in the Republic of Kazakhstan, foreign language instruction is aimed at developing a multicultural linguistic personality – an individual capable of engaging in dialogue on professional and social topics, while also articulately expressing their position and critically analyzing information in a foreign language (On approval of the State Program for the Implementation of Language Policy in the Republic of Kazakhstan for 2020-2025).

Classroom debates are one of the most effective methods for achieving this goal in English lessons in high school. It not only helps improve skills in all types of verbal activity (speaking, listening, reading, and writing) but also creates conditions for simulating real-life public debate situations, closely resembling intercultural communication. Debates also contribute to the development of meta-subject skills (analysis, synthesis, reflection, teamwork), which lays the foundation for students' future successful intercultural communication in the context of globalization and digitalization. For students aged 15–18, debates are particularly relevant, as participation in debates on various topics meets students' growing need for self-expression and social engagement, fosters critical thinking (in accordance with Vygotsky's theory, 1986), and prepares them for final assessments (the Unified National Testing, international exams), which require writing an essay with a reasoned justification for one's point of view.

Critical thinking is the ability to analyze information, identify logical connections, evaluate arguments, and make informed decisions. It plays a key role in the educational process, as it helps students not just memorize information but also engage with it meaningfully.

The relevance of this study stems from the need to implement innovative teaching methods that promote the development of students' critical thinking, as well as the insufficient understanding of the pedagogical potential of debates in educational practice. Despite the existence of research on interactive teaching methods, the systematic use of debates as a means of fostering critical thinking requires further theoretical understanding and practical justification.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the pedagogical potential of academic debates in developing students' critical thinking. In accordance with this goal, the following objectives have been defined: to examine the theoretical foundations of critical thinking in an educational context; to analyze the characteristics of debates as an interactive teaching method; to identify the pedagogical conditions for their effective use; and to determine the impact of debates on the development of students' critical thinking.

Materials and methods of research. The research method is an active learning method that involves the exchange of opinions between participants in the educational process with

the goal of seeking truth, developing solutions, or gaining a deeper understanding of a topic. Debate is based on dialogic interaction, during which students formulate arguments, analyze opponents' positions, draw conclusions, and refine their own perspectives. The method draws on various theoretical approaches:

Constructivism (J. Piaget, 1979; L. Vygotsky, 1986) suggests that knowledge is formed through active interaction, and discussion creates the conditions for the joint construction of meanings.

Critical pedagogy (P. Freire, 1973; J. Dewey, 1963) views learning as a process of dialogue, where students not only acquire knowledge but also learn to critically understand reality.

Dialogic pedagogy (M. Bakhtin, 1979; V. Bibler, 1989) emphasizes the importance of dialogue in the process of learning, where truth is born from the clash of different opinions. These approaches confirm that the discussion method contributes to the development of not only cognitive skills, but also personal qualities such as independence, tolerance, the ability to listen and express one's thoughts.

The debate method promotes the development of critical thinking through the following mechanisms:

Development of analytical skills – students learn to analyze different points of view and evaluate them reasonably.

Development of argumentative skills – during discussions, students learn to construct their speech logically, present evidence and counterarguments.

Information processing skills – requires searching, selecting, and interpreting data.

Reflection training – students reflect on their positions, adjust their views, and draw conclusions;

Actively engaging students in exploratory learning and cognitive activities based on intrinsic motivation;

Organizing joint activities, partnerships between teachers and students, and engaging children in pedagogically appropriate educational relationships in learning activities;

Ensuring dialogic communication between teacher and students and between students in the process of acquiring new knowledge.

The effectiveness of debates in education largely depends on the teacher's awareness of the possibility and appropriateness of their use. For instance, when studying a particular topic, not every topic can be the subject of debate; the topic must be clearly formulated. In a given class, the success of debates largely depends on a friendly, creative atmosphere in the classroom; the teacher must adequately assess the students' level of preparation required for conducting different types of debates. Debates can be used to summarize, systematize, assess knowledge, and reinforce material.

To achieve the set educational goals – the successful achievement of the set goals, achieved through debates, is determined by the teacher's ability to create conditions for effective interaction in the classroom; establishing trusting relationships with students, clearly defining the topic and scope of the material to be discussed, and the ability of the teacher and students to organize business communication.

Research results and discussion. Numerous studies confirm that systematically integrating debates into the classroom yields tangible results:

- A 30-35% increase in verbal fluency.
- A 20-25% increase in active vocabulary.
- Increased confidence in oral communication in 75-80% of participants.

Organizing debates, while engaging, can be fraught with challenges for teachers. The example of organizing a debate in an 11th-grade lesson on the topic of Green Belts (Green Belts: Pros and Cons), taken from the Spotlight 11 resource (Module 5, Going Green, p. 97).

The first limitation that occurs is that students are poorly prepared for debate. Insufficient English proficiency and a poor understanding of the debate topic among some students can lead to passivity and a lack of confidence in their statements. If such a lesson is organized spontaneously with students who have not worked with this method before and do not have the necessary vocabulary, nothing will come of it and the lesson will be ineffective, leaving some students feeling disappointed and inferior.

To address this issue, it is important to familiarize students with the topic before the debate. Discuss not only the topic of their upcoming speeches with them but also review the textbook's vocabulary to become familiar with speech clichés, stylistic argumentation techniques, and specialized vocabulary related to the topics "Ecology" and "Social Problems."

Students are divided into groups and asked them to analyze the texts, compiling lists of words, phrases for three categories:

- Terms related to the debate topic (e.g., urban sprawl; outdoor recreation; habitats for wildlife; shortage; nature conservation; nature reserves, etc.)
- Speech clichés for expressing opinions: I can't believe anyone would want to...; Why don't... instead?; People's lives are enriched by...; We should all oppose...; In my opinion...; ...is the answer!; In any case...; etc.

Stylistic devices for arguing a point of view:

- Emotional vocabulary and expression: can't believe, eaten up (a metaphor emphasizing the destructiveness of the process), ugly derelict land – creating a negative image of the alternative.
- Appeal to shared values: caring for nature, quality of life, aesthetics – appealing to socially accepted attitudes.
- Call to action: We should all oppose... – mobilizing the audience.
- Statement of the problem: England has a huge housing shortage problem – posing an urgent social issue that requires a solution.

Quantifiers and mitigation: a very small proportion of green belt land – emphasizing minimal intervention, reducing anxiety. The chain of cause and effect: long trips → traffic jams → CO₂ emissions – a logical argument for the harm of the current situation.

Separation of functions: As for nature conservation, that is not why green belts were created – deconstructing the myth/expectation, redirecting the focus to other tools (national parks, nature reserves).

Alternative solution: proposing a specific solution (building on a very small proportion...) as a rational alternative – a pragmatic tone.

The second drawback is ignorance of the rules of debate, a misunderstanding of the essence of this method. To organize debates within a lesson, the teacher should discuss with students what this type of oral presentation entails and outline the rules for conducting the discussion. For example, only facts and logic, no emotional outburst emphasizes facts and logic as the basis for argumentation, minimizing emotional tension.

Listen to your opponent and answer: "What did you learn from your opponent?" – reflect, be sure to comment on what you learned from your opponent's position.

In the absence of clear regulation and moderation mechanisms, debates can degenerate into unproductive verbal sparring rather than constructive dialogue.

The third obstacle is that debates are unpredictable, meaning the need to quickly come up with counterarguments can cause stress for some students and lead to superficial judgments.

To address this challenge, you can include a rule for timeouts – short 30-second breaks for internal team consultations – during a debate-style lesson. It would also be helpful to familiarize students with cross-examination techniques (the ability to ask opposing questions promptly and accurately).

The simplest solution to accustoming students to stress-free debate techniques is to gradually increase the difficulty of assignments: moving from short discussions of texts read/videos watched in pairs and small groups to full-fledged debates.

Various debate models can be successfully applied in high school:

- Debate as work with text/video: Students analyze the provided material (article, video) and formulate positions consistent with their team role.
- Express debate: A format with minimal preparation, where a significant portion of the argumentation is based on the textbook or provided materials.
- Speed Debating: A one-on-one competition that requires prompt responses to the opponent's questions.
- Karl Popper's Classic Debate: A structured model with two teams of three, strict role assignments, and a set schedule (Popper, 1985).

The full debate cycle (preparation, presentation, discussion) often exceeds the standard 45-60 minutes. Therefore, for greater efficiency, it is recommended to divide the process into at least two stages, distributing them across different lessons: Lesson 1: vocabulary study, argument collection, and preparation; Lesson 2: the debate itself, analysis, and reflection.

Assessing the quality of argumentation and the flow of the debate can be subjective and difficult to quantify. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare evaluation criteria in advance and familiarize the debate participants with them. Criteria may include, for example:

- Linguistic accuracy (clarity of phonetics, grammar, and vocabulary used in the presentation).
- Logical argumentation (arguments are supported by examples, supplemented by possible outcomes, etc.).
- Interaction with the opponent (politeness, ability to listen and hear questions, participation in team timeouts and clarifying questions, etc.).

Student self-assessments on the proposed scale (e.g., "I used 5 new words," "I refuted 2 arguments").

In summary, it should be noted that debate method integrated into English lessons is not just a trendy interactive method, but a strategic tool for developing students' key competencies necessary for successful life in a globalized world. Debates fully meet modern requirements for students' communicative training, developing their ability to engage in dialogue and mutual understanding; they systematically develop both linguistic and cognitive skills, encompassing vocabulary, grammar, critical thinking, and analytical abilities. This model also develops socially significant competencies, such as productive teamwork, respect for diversity of opinion, and the ability to constructively defend one's position. However, it is important to remember that using debates in a lesson requires careful organization and pedagogical skill to minimize potential risks, such as language barriers or excessive emotional tension.

The example of the Green Belts debate demonstrates that even complex socio-environmental issues can serve as effective learning material if certain conditions are met, such as adequate language support through the provision of necessary templates, glossaries, and preparatory stages; a clearly structured process; a transparent and understandable assessment system; and opportunities for self-reflection for students.

Conclusion. The study examined the pedagogical potential of academic debates as an effective interactive teaching method aimed at developing students' critical thinking. An analysis of theoretical sources and teaching practices revealed that debates contribute to the development of key cognitive and communicative skills, including the ability to analyze information, construct logical arguments, evaluate different points of view, and formulate one's own position.

It has been established that the use of debates in the educational process activates students' cognitive activity, increases their level of engagement, and promotes the development

of independent thinking skills. Furthermore, this method fosters a culture of academic discussion and a tolerant attitude toward alternative opinions, which is especially important in today's information society.

However, the effectiveness of debates depends on a number of pedagogical conditions, including a methodologically sound organization of the process, clearly structured assignments, and the creation of a supportive educational environment. This underscores the need for targeted training of teachers in the use of this method.

Thus, academic debates possess significant pedagogical potential and can be considered an effective means of developing critical thinking in the modern education system. Prospects for further research include studying the impact of debates in combination with digital technologies, as well as their adaptation to various levels and contexts of learning.

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